

The relationship between organizational culture and organizational innovation of physical education teachers in Ghorveh city

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Abstract

To know the organization and behavior and performance of employees, it is necessary to understand the culture of that organization. Therefore, the purpose of this research was to study of the relationship between organizational culture and organizational innovation of physical education teachers in Ghorveh city. The population consisted of all physical education teachers in Ghorveh city (N= 50). The population was equal to the sample. Randsip (1986) organizational innovation standard questionnaire and Robbins (1991) organizational culture standard questionnaire were used to collect data. The results showed there was significant relationship between organizational culture and organizational innovation. Also, Innovation, leadership, support, Integration, control and Identity had significant relationship with teachers' innovation, But Risk Taking, Reward System, compromise with conflict phenomenon and communication patterns hadn't significant relationship with teachers' innovation. Also, results of Multiple Regression showed that organizational culture has capability of prediction of organizational innovation to 47 percent and among organizational culture factors; control had an important predictor for organizational innovation. With respect to these results, it is necessary to notice to this factor as an effective factor for enhancement of organizational innovation.

Key Words: Organizational culture, Creativity, Teacher

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